

Hawking temperature and the entropic force of a Schwarzschild black hole

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Abstract

A black hole is considered a thermodynamic macrosystem; however, we derive an expression to quantify its entropic force by studying the first law of thermodynamics. We report that this force is inversely proportional to the square of the mass and directly proportional to the radius of the black hole. It may aid in a better understanding of black hole thermodynamics.

According to study by Bekenstien [1] and Hawking [2] black holes are not completely black but emit photons in form of radiation due to the quantum-gravitational effect and this idea laid the foundation of black hole thermodynamics in physics [3] [4], however, in this context, black holes have entropy and a finite temperature and equivalent to a physical thermodynamical system; thus at its horizon it has temperature and therefore must be considered as macro-system which occupy a large number of states.

In this scenario, it might have entropic force related to the presence of the horizon. The derivation of the mathematical expression of entropic force for a black hole is the objective of this paper, and we make an effort to derive it. To do this, we use the idea of black hole thermodynamics, where its first law states that:

$$\nabla E = T \nabla S \quad (1)$$

where E is energy and T and S are temperature and entropy, respectively. This states that the energy of the system is simply a function of temperature and the entropy of a black hole [5] [6]. As is well known, a Schwarzschild black hole is only defined by its mass; thus, to cal-

culate the entropic force of a black hole in the context of thermodynamics [7], we use Eq.(1) and rewrite it as follows:

$$\nabla F_R = \frac{T \nabla S}{\nabla R} \quad (2)$$

here F_R is entropic force, and R is the space parameter, in case of black hole its just Schwarzschild radius. This shows the force in terms of temperature and entropy [7].

Next, by substituting the Hawking temperature $T = \frac{hc^3}{Gmk_B}$ where h , c , G , m , k_B is Planck constant, speed of light, gravitational constant, mass of black hole, Boltzmann constant respectively and entropy $\nabla S = \frac{R^2 c^3}{Gh} k_B$ in Eq.(2), it yields,

$$F_R = \frac{R^2 c^8}{m^2 G^3} \quad (3)$$

it denotes entropic force of a black hole.

From Eq.(3), one can observe that the force is directly proportional to the square of the space parameter and inversely proportional to the square of the mass. This entropic force is function of mass and space and simply inverse of inverse square law of force. Thus, by making an analogy with classical gravity, we can say this force is just an inverted version of Newton's classical gravity, however, in the context

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of black hole thermodynamics, one can say that classical gravity has been inverted and emerged as entropic force.

In terms of entropy ∇S it will be as followings,

$$F_R = \left(\frac{\nabla S}{k_B} \right) \frac{hc^5}{G^2 m^2} \quad (4)$$

this shows the force is directly proportional to entropy of the system or a black hole.

Further, by substituting the R as the Planck length in Eq.(3) we get the followings,

$$F_R = \frac{hc^5}{G^2 m^2} \quad (5)$$

this is other form of entropic force of black hole and only function of mass m .

By taking $P = \frac{F}{A}$ where A is the area, the Eq. (5) corresponds to the followings,

$$P = \frac{hc^9}{G^4 m^4} \quad (6)$$

this shows the pressure of black hole, however, on this basis one can say that the entropic force and pressure of black hole corresponds to each other mathematically.

To summarise, a black hole has an entropic force that is directly proportional to its radius and inversely proportional to the square of its mass. It suggests that a larger, lighter black hole will have a higher entropic force. This force has a correlation with the black hole's temperature and pressure. It may add knowledge about black hole thermodynamics.

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